

HEDGING AS A PRAGMATIC UNIVERSAL CHARACTERISTIC OF SCIENTIFIC DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article examines the phenomenon of hedging as a communicative tactic widely used in modern English language scientific discourse. English, serving as the global medium of international scientific communication, imposes specific requirements regarding the formalisation and precision of statements. Hedging, understood as the deliberate use of evasive, indefinite, or softened formulations, allows authors to reduce the categorical nature of assertions, demonstrate openness to discussion, observe the principles of politeness, and follow the conventions of scientific style.

Keywords: hedging, scientific discourse, communicative tactic, pragmatics, hedging devices, epistemic modality, politeness.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy ingliz tilidagi ilmiy nutqda keng qo'llaniladigan kommunikativ taktik sifatida hedging fenomenini o'rganadi. Ingliz tili xalqaro ilmiy aloqa global vositasi sifatida bayonotlarning rasmiylashtirilishi va aniqligiga oid maxsus talablarni qo'yadi. Hedging, qasddan qochqin, noaniq yoki yumshatilgan shakllardan foydalanish sifatida tushuniladi, mualliflarga da'volarning kategorikligini pasaytirish, muhokamaga ochiqlik ko'rsatish, xushmuomalalik tamoyillariga rioya qilish va ilmiy uslub konvensiyalariga amal qilish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: hedjing, ilmiy nutq, kommunikativ taktik, pragmatika, hedjing vositalari, epistemik modallik, xushmuomalalik.

Аннотация

В статье исследуется феномен хеджирования как коммуникативной тактики, широко используемой в современном англоязычном научном дискурсе. Английский язык, выступая в роли глобального средства международного научного общения, предъявляет специфические требования к формализации и точности высказываний. Хеджирование, понимаемое как целенаправленное использование уклончивых, неопределенных или смягченных формулировок, позволяет авторам снижать категоричность утверждений, демонстрировать открытость к дискуссии, соблюдать принципы вежливости и следовать конвенциям научного стиля.

Ключевые слова: хеджирование, научный дискурс, коммуникативная тактика, прагматика, средства хеджирования, эпистемическая модальность, вежливость.

Since English has firmly established itself as the language of international scientific communication, a comprehensive study of the linguistic characteristics of modern English-language scientific discourse becomes a pressing task. The results obtained can be effectively used in teaching English for Academic Purposes (EAP) as well as in preparing students for studying in a foreign-language educational

environment. Unlike everyday communication, the language of scientific description is formalised and follows explicit and implicit rules and conventions, with hedging devices making a significant contribution to this formalisation. The term “hedging” originally gained currency in economic theory and business, where it denotes operations aimed at risk management. Etymologically, the term goes back to the English word *hedge* (“fence, living fence”) and the verb *to hedge* (“to surround with a fence”).

In linguistics, hedging is understood as a specific communicative tactic involving the deliberate use of evasive, indefinite, or softened statements, which is achieved through a range of linguistic means. In written scientific discourse, hedges serve to realise the following communicative intentions:

Shifting responsibility and softening categoricalness - the author softens direct assertions, reducing personal responsibility for the proposition and preventing or weakening possible objections from opponents.

Demonstrating openness and epistemic caution - the author shows the reader that they do not claim absolute truth, are open to discussion, or recognize that the available data are insufficient for definitive conclusions.

Politeness and tact (negative politeness) - the author observes the maxims of modesty and tact: softening praise of their own achievements and smoothing out criticism directed at opponents, thereby taking into account the “face” of the reader or opponent.

Following scientific conventions and integration into the community (positive politeness) - the use of hedges demonstrates the author’s genre competence and their desire to be accepted into the scientific community.

Discourse analysis of English-language scientific articles on economics and business has made it possible to identify the following groups of lexical hedges:

Group	Examples	Illustration
Modal verbs	<i>may, might, could, would</i>	<i>Researchers might consider sampling...</i>
Epistemic verbs	<i>believe, assume, suggest, estimate, think, argue, indicate, propose</i>	<i>Given the small sample size, we believe...</i>
Perception verbs with a modal component	<i>seem, appear, tend</i>	<i>firms tend to be better performers</i>
Adjectives / adverbs of probability	<i>possible, (un)likely, probable, probably, perhaps</i>	<i>Perhaps the most important finding...</i>
Approximators	<i>about, approximately, roughly, pretty, a (little) bit, often, occasionally, generally, usually, somewhat, somehow, quite</i>	<i>*...approximately 2.5 mol/s*</i>

Structural-grammatical devices include:

The pronouns *we / our* – they function as self-reference and also serve as a means of inclusivity and solidarity with the scientific community (e.g., *Previously, we empirically examined...; Our recent research suggests...*).

Introductory phrases with epistemic verbs - they introduce the author's opinion (e.g., *We believe that there is no simple explanation*).

Phrases referring to the source of knowledge – *according to, it is known, it is common knowledge, as Drucker suggested, several studies have suggested, on the basis of previous research*.

The “nominative with infinitive” construction – especially with *likely/unlikely* (e.g., *Customers are likely to treat technological innovations as...*).

Impersonal constructions with adjectives and verbs from the lexical hedging inventory: *It is conceivable; It is important to note; It has been argued that...*

Quite often, to enhance the effect of reducing categoricalness, authors combine several hedging devices simultaneously, for example: *it would seem somewhat unlikely that, we should perhaps acknowledge that*.

In English for Academic Purposes (EAP) courses, systematic attention should be paid to the hedging devices listed above. Students must not only understand the pragmatic effects of utterances containing hedges but also be able themselves to adequately express their communicative intentions in accordance with the existing norms of scientific speech. Cross-linguistic studies carried out on the basis of different languages make it possible to identify both universal and culture-specific manifestations of hedging as a communicative tactic [1; 2]. This confirms that hedging can be regarded as a **pragmatic universal** of scientific discourse, although the specific linguistic devices and their frequency may vary depending on the language and national academic tradition.

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